

Studies in the Substituted and Unsubstituted 8-Hydroxyquinoline-4-(*N*-*p*-chloromethylphenyl)sulphonamide Metal Chelates : Synthetic and Bacteriological

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Several quinoline derivatives are used in medicinal chemistry. Urea derivatives of quinoline¹ are used as analgesic and central nervous system depressant, 8-aminoquinolines as antimalarials², 8-hydroxyquinolines as amoebicides and phenothiazines as insecticides³.

N-Amino acid ester substituted 8-hydroxyquinoline 4 or 5 sulphonamides have been prepared. Better biological activities were found in the metal chelates than in the organic ligands⁴. In this context, the study of the bacteriological activity of some metal chelates of substituted and unsubstituted 8-hydroxyquinoline-(*N*-*p*-chloromethylphenyl) sulphonamide appears useful.

Experimental

8-Hydroxyquinoline was prepared by the known method⁵. The 5,7-dinitro-, 5,7-diamino-, 5-bromo-, 5-methyl-, 5-chloro- and 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinolines were also prepared.

portion, was heated at 50–60°. The pH of the solution was maintained at 8–9 by using a solution of 0.1 *N* NaOH (8.5–21.3 ml) and 1.0 *M* H₃BO₃ (50 ml). The resulting solid chelate was washed with hot water and crystallised from 50% acetic acid. The m.ps. of the chelates were found to be more than 300°.

Antibacterial activity of ligand: The antibacterial activity was determined by cup-plate agar diffusion technique⁶. The compounds were found to be active against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *S. comma*.

The magnetic susceptibility of the metal chelates were determined by Gouy method. The ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 580 spectrophotometer. Ir data (Table 1) indicate that on complex formation there is shifting of the bands in comparison to the spectra of the ligands.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} B.M	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹
	Metal	N	C	H	Cl		
(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ SN ₂ Cl) ₂ Cu	8.32	7.34	50.36	3.67	9.31	1.75	14 500
	(8.30)	7.36	50.35	3.69	9.33	1.70)	15 900
(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ SN ₂ Cl) ₂ Fe	7.39	7.41	50.87	3.70	9.40	3.60	26 000
	(7.35)	7.39	50.89	3.72	9.42	3.62)	25 347
(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ SN ₂ Cl) ₂ Co	7.77	7.38	50.66	3.69	9.36	4.72	28 563
	(7.79)	7.36	50.68	3.70	9.34	4.70)	26 123
(C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ SN ₂ Cl) ₂ Cd	13.8	6.90	47.32	3.45	8.75	5.61	29 423
	(13.8)	6.85	47.36	3.42	8.76	5.63)	28 326

Preparation of ligands: 8-Hydroxyquinoline-4-sulphonyl chloride prepared by the known method, was dissolved in alcohol and to it a solution of *p*-chloromethylaniline (A.R.) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The resulting grey coloured solid was washed with alcohol, dried and crystallised from hot water to yield white crystals.

Preparation of metal chelates: A mixture of water-soluble salt of Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} or Cd^{II} and aqueous solution of the ligand in definite pro-

References

1. L. BERNARD, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, 71, 81208.
2. W. SCHULEMANN and F. METZSCH, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1930, 24, 4588.
3. S. BERNTHSEN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1833, 16, 2896.
4. D. R. WILLIAMS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1972, 72, 203; A. FENST and R. T. HARAT, *Prog. Exp. Tumor Res.*, 1969, 12, 102.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London.
6. H. VOGT and P. JESKI, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1958, 191, 168; G. D. TIWARI and M. N. MISHRA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1980, 49, 8.